

Synthesis, spectroscopic and biological characterization of the Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with a new macrocyclic tetradentate [N₄] ligand

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Manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes having the general composition M(L)X₂ (Where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, L = ligand and X stands for Cl and NO₃) have been prepared with 2,4,10,12-tetramethyl, 1,5,9,13-tetraazacyclohexadeca, 1,4,9,12-tetraene (ligand). The complexes have been characterised by elemental analyses, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements, ¹H NMR, IR, electronic, mass and EPR spectral studies. All the complexes are of high spin type and found to have six coordinated geometry. The biological activities of the ligand and complexes have been screened in vitro against some bacteria and pathogenic fungi to study their capacity to inhibit their growth.

Synthetic macrocyclic complexes of transition metals have attracted much attention as promising objects in coordination and supramolecular chemistry¹. Transition metal complexes of these ligands are also widely studied because of their potential therapeutic uses². They are also useful in health and skin care products and in paint manufacturing³. Our present study focused on the complexation behavior of the biologically and important ions⁴, manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II), with nitrogen donor systems. They are especially suitable for such investigations⁵, since they tend not to exhibit the high thermodynamic and kinetic stabilities that are frequently characteristic of all complexes of nitrogen donor macrocyclic ligands⁶.

In this paper we report the results of the structure, function relationship under lying metal ion binding by the tetradentate nitrogen donor [N₄] macrocyclic ligand L (Fig. 1), incorporating 16-membered backbone with each of the above metal ion.

Fig. 1. Synthesis and structure of ligand (L).

Results and discussion

On the basis of elemental analyses, the complexes were assigned to have the composition shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO correspond to non-electrolytes⁷. Therefore these complexes may be formulated as [M(L)X₂] where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and X = Cl and NO₃. The mass spectrum of ligand (L) confirm the proposed formula by showing a peak at 275 amu corresponding to the macrocyclic moiety [(C₁₆H₂₈N₄)⁺ atomic mass 276]. It also shows a series of peaks i.e. 15, 30, 42, 68, 70, 138, 142, 208 and 233 amu corresponding to various fragments of the compound. Their intensity gives an idea of stability of fragments. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand, the presence of the middle -CH₂ protons (8H) is confirmed by the appearance of a signal at δ 1.9–2.2¹², an expected quintet. The presence of a sharp triplet at δ 1.4–1.6 ppm may be assigned to -CH₃ protons (12H). Another signal appeared at δ 6.82–7.11 ppm as a doublet may be assigned for the protons of (C-CH₂-N) (8H). In the IR spectrum of ligand (L) the absence of absorption around 3400 cm⁻¹ indicates that the free amino group is not present. No bands were observed around the ~1700–1800 cm⁻¹ which indicates elimination of water molecule in the ligand⁸. The characteristic bands due to chelated ligand appear at 1500–1700 cm⁻¹. The bands at 1375 and 1428 cm⁻¹ are due to C-CH₃ and -CH₂- groups. Absence of band at ~1720 cm⁻¹ corresponding to free carbonyl group in the IR spectrum of the ligand indicates that complete condensation takes place. The band at 1589 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν(C=N)^{9,10}. The shifting of the band of ν(C=N) toward the lower side in the complexes indicates

Table 1. Physico-chemical and electronic spectral data of the complexes*

Complex	MW	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Colour	M.p. °C	Yield %	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})
$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_4$ (ligand)	276	–	Cream	245	72		
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	302	10.53	Pale	286	68	6.01	17908, 25000, 29156, 31211
$\text{MnC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$			brown				
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	455	10.48	Light	266	66	5.96	18210, 24986, 28884, 31280
$\text{MnC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{N}_6$			brown				
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	406	13.00	Dark	259	64	4.98	8827, 14476, 21055
$\text{CoC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$			brown				
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	459	12.81	Pink	263	66	5.02	8693, 14541, 18656
$\text{CoC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6$							
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	406	11.20	Light	291	70	2.94	9997, 16642, 24867
$\text{NiC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$			green				
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	459	10.70	Shiny	287	68	2.98	10526, 16257, 24876
$\text{NiC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$			blue				
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	411	12.80	Navy	288	66	1.99	10219, 14448, 20234
$\text{CuC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2$			blue				
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	464	10.40	Brown	273	68	2.01	10348, 14640, 20161
$\text{CuC}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$							

that the coordination takes place through the nitrogen of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group, which indicates that the ligand (L) behaves as tetradentate.

IR spectra of the complexes :

IR spectra of nitrate complexes display absorption bands at $\sim 1424\text{--}1431$ (ν_1), $1366\text{--}1369$ (ν_3), $1209\text{--}1211$ (ν_5), $1018\text{--}1019$ (ν_2) and $832\text{--}834$ (ν_4) suggesting that both the nitrate groups are coordinated to the central metal ion and the separation of $\sim 220\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate their unidentate nature¹¹.

Manganese(II) complexes :

The Mn^{II} complexes show magnetic moments corresponding to five unpaired electrons (5.96–6.01 B.M.) at RT (Table 1), close to the spin only value of 5.92 B.M.

Electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes display weak absorption bands at $17908\text{--}18210$ (ν_1) ($\epsilon = 38\text{--}44\text{ dm}^3$

$\text{mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$), $24986\text{--}25000$ (ν_2) ($\epsilon = 47\text{--}51\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$), $28884\text{--}29156$ (ν_3) ($\epsilon = 59\text{--}62\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $31211\text{--}31280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_4) ($\epsilon = 119\text{--}127\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Table 1) characteristic of the octahedral geometry¹². In these complexes these bands may be assigned to the transitions : ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g} ({}^4G)$ ($10B + 5C$), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g ({}^4D)$ ($17B + 5C$) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4P)$ ($7B + 7C$), respectively. The experimentally observed transition energies and calculated values of parameters B , C , Dq and β are listed in Table 2.

The EPR spectra of the complexes have been recorded in polycrystalline state and in the solution of DMSO. Polycrystalline samples gives one broad signal centered at approximately the free electron g value (Table 5). The g values lie in the range 2.01–2.06.

Table 2. Ligand field parameters of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	C (cm^{-1})	ν_2/ν_1	F_4	F_2	H_x	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})
$[[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	1790.8	593	0.75	3814	1.40	109	1138	3.57	0
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1821.0	557	0.71	3883	1.37	111	1112	4.14	0
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	1033.4	1076	0.96	–	1.64	–	–	–	98.77
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1017.7	1060	0.95	–	1.67	–	–	–	97.27
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	999.7	768	0.73	3071	1.66	–	–	–	143.30
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1052.6	637	0.61	2548	1.54	–	–	–	150.90

DMSO solution the complexes give EPR spectra containing six lines arising due to hyperfine interaction between the unpaired electrons with the ^{55}Mn nucleus ($I = 5/2$). The nuclear magnetic quantum number, M_I , corresponding to the lines $-5/2, -3/2, -1/2, +1/2, +3/2, 5/2$ from low to high field.

Cobalt(II) complexes :

At RT the magnetic moment values of the cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.98–5.02 B.M. corresponding to three unpaired electrons (Table 1).

The electronic spectra of all the cobalt(II) complexes exhibit absorption in the region 8693–8827 ($\epsilon = 53\text{--}57 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 14476–14541 ($\epsilon = 68\text{--}73 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 18656–21055 ($\epsilon = 91\text{--}97 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). These bands may be assigned to the following transitions: ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. These transitions suggest an octahedral environment^{13–16} around the cobalt ion.

EPR spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes was recorded in polycrystalline state at LNT because the rapid spin relaxation of Co^{II} broadens the line at higher temperature. g_{iso} values of these complexes were in the range 2.01–2.03 (Table 5).

Nickel(II) complexes :

At RT these complexes show magnetic moment in the range 2.94–2.98 B.M. These values correspond to a high spin configuration and show the presence of an octahedral environment⁵ around the Ni^{II} ion in the complexes.

The electronic spectra of the complexes display three absorption bands in the range 9997–10526 ($\epsilon = 36\text{--}42 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 16257–16642 ($\epsilon = 66\text{--}73 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 24867–24876 ($\epsilon = 121\text{--}127 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). These bands may be assigned to the three spin allowed transitions: ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively, corresponding to an octahedral geometry^{12,13,15}.

Copper(II) complexes :

The magnetic moment measurements of the Cu^{II} complexes at RT lie in the range 1.99–2.01 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron.

Electronic spectra of copper complexes display bands in the range 10219–10348 ($\epsilon = 62\text{--}65 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_1), 14448–14640 ($\epsilon = 76\text{--}81 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_2) and 20161–20234 ($\epsilon = 127\text{--}132 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_3). These bands may be considered to the following three spin allowed transitions¹³: ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) (ν_1), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{zy}$) (ν_2) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{zy}, d_{yz}$) (ν_3).

These transitions suggests D_{4h} symmetry.

The EPR spectra of the complexes, recorded in polycrystalline state at RT show anisotropic spectra which is characteristic of tetragonal Cu^{II} . g Values have been calculated by Kneubuhl's method⁹. The g values observed in the range 2.05–2.12.

$G = (g_{\parallel}-2) / (g_{\perp}-2)$, which is the measurement of the exchange interaction between copper centers in a polycrystalline solid, was calculated. According to Hathaway¹⁴, in the reported Cu^{II} complex the G value are <4 indicating the exchange interaction in solid complex.

Ligand field parameters :

Various ligand field parameters¹⁰ were calculated for the complexes and are listed in Table 2. The values of Dq in Co^{II} complexes were calculated from transition energy ratio diagram using the ν_3/ν_2 ratio. The results are in agreement with the respective position of anions in the spectrochemical series. The Nephelauxetic parameter β were readily obtained by using the relation :

$$\beta = B(\text{Complex}) / B(\text{Free ion})$$

where $B(\text{Free ion})$ for Mn^{II} is 786, for Co^{II} is 1120 and for Ni^{II} is 1041 cm^{-1} . The values of β lies in the range of 0.61–0.96. The values indicate the appreciable covalent character of metal ligand σ bond. The value of B and C for Mn^{II} are calculated from the second transitions because this transition is free from the crystal field splitting and depend on B and C parameters. The calculated values of the ligand field parameters are given in Table 2.

Biological screening :

The ligand (L) and its complexes were evaluated against several bacteria and different pathogenic fungi.

Antibacterial screening :

The antibacterial action of the ligand and the complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} was checked¹⁴ by the disc diffusion technique. This was done on *Sarcina lutea* (gram-positive), *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherchia coli* (gram-negative) bacteria at 35°. The disc of Whatmann no. 4 filter paper having the diameter 6.00 mm were soaked in the solution of compounds in DMSO [Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs)¹⁸ were in the range 40–45, 49–62, 27–46, 21–32 and 12–22 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for ligand (L), Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , respectively] (Table 4). After drying it was placed on nutrient agar plates. The inhibition areas were observed after 48 h. DMSO was used as a control and Gentamycin as a standard drug.

100% growth of bacteria which is represented as +, 50% growth by ++, less than 50% growth by +++ and noble

inhibition by +++++. Ligand shows moderate inhibition against all the species. Mn^{II} complexes are less active than ligand while Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes gives almost similar inhibition capacity. Cu^{II} complexes were found to have the maximum inhibition capacity against all the bacterial species, under study. The bacterial growth inhibition capacity of the complexes are in the order : Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II} given in Table 3.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity and standard drug comparison data of the ligand and complexes

Compd.	Bacterial inhibition (%) (MIC in µg ml ⁻¹)		
	<i>Sarcina lutea</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherchia coli</i>
Ligand (L)	++ (40)	++ (48)	++ (45)
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	++ (45)	++ (48)	++ (48)
[Mn(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	+ (62)	++ (49)	++ (56)
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	+++ (32)	++ (43)	++ (45)
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	+++ (27)	+++ (36)	++ (46)
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	+++ (28)	+++ (30)	++ (32)
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	+++ (25)	+++ (21)	+++ (32)
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	+++ (21)	++++ (19)	++++ (18)
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	++++ (17)	+++ (22)	++++ (12)
Streptomycin*	++++ (1.5)	++++ (1)	++++ (2)
Gentamycin*	++++ (1)	++++ (1)	++++ (1.5)
Desmycosin*	-	++++ (1)	+ (128)
Tylosin*	-	++++ (1)	++ (64)

* Standard drugs²⁰.

Antifungal screening :

The antifungal activity of the ligand and its transition metal complexes under study were checked, by the agar plate technique¹⁹ for the *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus glaucus*, *Ustilago tritici* and *Ustilago scitamineae* fungi. The compounds were directly mixed to the medium in different concentrations [MICs = 43–79, 42–59, 24–44, 20–28 and 8–20 µg ml⁻¹ for ligand (L), Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, respectively] (Table 4). The fungus was placed on the medium with the help of the inoculum needle. The pettridishes were wrapped in polythene sheets, containing some drops of EtOH and put in incubator at 32 ± 1° for 48–72 h. The growth of fungus was measured by the recording the diameter of fungal colony. The following relation calculated the fungal growth inhibition :

$$\text{Fungal growth inhibition \%} = (A - B) \times 100 / A$$

where A = diameter of fungal colony in control plate, B= diameter of fungal colony in test plate.

100% growth of fungus which is represented as *, 50% growth by **, less then 50% growth by *** and noble inhibition by ****.

Table 4. Antifungal activity data of the ligand and complexes

Compd.	Fungal inhibition % (MIC in µg ml ⁻¹)			
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Aspergillus glaucus</i>	<i>Ustilago tritici</i>	<i>Ustilago scitamineae</i>
Ligand (L)	** (57)	* (79)	** (43)	* (66)
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	* (59)	** (53)	** (42)	** (46)
[Mn(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	** (50)	* (58)	* (56)	** (40)
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	** (27)	*** (24)	** (31)	** (44)
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	*** (25)	** (36)	*** (26)	** (29)
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	*** (20)	*** (23)	*** (28)	** (24)
[Ni(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	*** (21)	*** (24)	** (28)	*** (20)
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	**** (13)	**** (20)	**** (08)	**** (17)
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	*** (22)	*** (21)	**** (16)	*** (22)
Streptomycin ^a	**** (1)	-	**** (1)	-
Gentamycin ^a	**** (1.5)	-	**** (1.5)	-

^aStandard drugs.

Table 5. EPR spectral data of the complexes (as polycrystalline sample)

Complexes	Data at LNT and room temperature (as polycrystalline sample)			
	g	g _⊥	g _{iso}	G
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	-	-	2.06	-
[Mn(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	-	-	2.01	-
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	2.05	2.02	2.03	-
[Co(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.03	2.00	2.01	-
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	2.14	2.11	2.12	1.27
[Cu(L)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.09	2.03	2.05	3.00

Ligand, Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes shows maximum inhibition against *U. tritici* while overall minimum activity shown by metal free ligand. Cu^{II} complexes were found to exhibits noble antifungal activity against all the species. The order of fungal growth inhibition capacity is Cu > Ni > Co > Mn > Ligand. The results of antifungal activity are shown in Table 4.

The results of the antibacterial and antifungal screening of the newly synthesized macrocyclic compounds with different species are given in Tables 3 and 4, which are compared with some standard drugs viz. *Streptomycin*, *Gentamycin*, *Desmycosin* and *Tylosin*²⁰ (Tables 3, 4).

The results of the biological screening indicate that the complexes are more active than free ligand. Increased activity of the complexes can be explained on the basis of chelation theory²⁴. The orbital of each metal ion is made so as to overlap with the ligand orbital. Increase enhances the lipophilicity of complexes due to delocalization of π-electrons in the chelate ring²².

The results of antibacterial and antifungal screening, indicates that Cu^{II} complexes show more activity than the other metal complexes. These may be due to the higher stability of the Cu^{II} complexes than the other complexes²³. It indicates that Cu^{II} ion is made up of stronger interactions with N donor atoms in ligand with Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions²³.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade, and procured from Fluka. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck used as received. All solvents used were purified according to standard procedure.

Synthesis of ligand :

The hot ethanolic solution 20 ml each of acetylacetone (5.000 g, 0.05 mol) and 1,3-diaminopropane (3.700 g, 0.05 mol) were mixed slowly with constant stirring. This mixture was refluxed at 77° for 6 h in the presence of few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. On cooling a solid cream-colored precipitate is formed, which was filtered, washed with cold EtOH, and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Yield 72%, m.p. 245° (Found : C, 69.48; H, 10.11; N, 20.19. Calcd. for C₁₆H₂₈N₄ (atomic mass 276) : C, 69.56; H, 10.15, N, 20.29%).

Synthesis of complexes :

The hot ethanolic solution 20 ml each of ligand (0.552 g, 0.002 mol) and of corresponding metal salts (0.001 mol) were mixed together with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 5–10 h at 65–80°. On cooling, colored complex precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Physical measurements :

The C, H and N were analysed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on a Elico (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at RT on a Faraday balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as a calibrant. Electron impact mass spectra were recorded on Jeol, JMS, DX-303 mass spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Hitachi FT-NMR, R-600 spectrometer using DMSO as solvent. The chemical shifts are given in ppm relative to TMS. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a FTIR Spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample and in the solution of DMSO, at LNT for Co^{II} and at RT for Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes on E₄-EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the g-marker.

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